

Supplementary Materials for: Analysis on non-monotone control-limit condition-based maintenance policies

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Abstract—This study delves into the challenge of optimizing Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM) for k -out-of- N systems characterized by economic dependencies, utilizing an average cost Markov Decision Process (MDP) formalism for a detailed analysis of optimal policies. Traditionally, CBM optimization presumes a monotone control-limit policy where the degradation level of components exceeds predefined thresholds. Recent investigations have visually demonstrated that the optimal CBM policy exhibits a non-monotone structure. Our analysis reveals that although the optimal bias functions exhibit partial monotonicity, this characteristic alone does not guarantee a monotone CBM policy. The emergence of non-monotonicity is attributed to the dynamics of the transition matrix influenced by preventive maintenance activities. Additionally, we show that the cost function is subadditive, indicating that the presence of setup costs significantly influences maintenance decisions, where this subadditivity also affects the formation of non-monotone regions in the optimal policy. Our findings indicate that non-monotone regions persist even in the absence of economic dependencies. Sensitivity analysis further reveals that higher cost parameters and reliability structure reduce the ratio of non-monotone regions, enhancing system stability. This study emphasizes the complex interdependence between reliability structure and cost parameters in shaping optimal CBM policies.

Index Terms—Group Maintenance, Markov Decision Process, Average Cost, hazard function, Control-limit policy, Phase-type distribution

I. PROOFS

Proof of Lemma 1. The difference $q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{a}) - q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a})$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{a}) - q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}) &= \sum_{\mathbf{j} \geq \mathbf{x}} p_{as(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{a}), \mathbf{j}} - \sum_{\mathbf{j} \geq \mathbf{x}} p_{as(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}), \mathbf{j}} \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{j} \geq \mathbf{x}} \prod_{n=1}^N \left(q_{as(\mathbf{s}', a_n), j_n}^{(n)} - q_{as(\mathbf{s}, a_n), j_n}^{(n)} \right) \\ &\geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Given that we assume $\mathbf{s} \preceq \mathbf{s}'$, using Assumption 2 which considers only the wear-out phase, it follows that $as(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{a}) \succeq$

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$as(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a})$. Therefore, $q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a})$ is element-wise monotonic increasing with respect to \mathbf{s} .

Proof of Lemma 2. The difference $c(\mathbf{s}_2, \mathbf{a}) - c(\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{a})$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} c(\mathbf{s}_2, \mathbf{a}) - c(\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{a}) &= c_s \left[1 - \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} (1 - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}_2 \in \mathcal{D}\}}) \right] \\ &\quad - c_s \left[1 - \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} (1 - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}_1 \in \mathcal{D}\}}) \right] \\ &\quad + c_F \cdot 1_{\{\mathbf{s}_2 \in \mathcal{D}\}} - c_F \cdot 1_{\{\mathbf{s}_1 \in \mathcal{D}\}} \\ &= c_s \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} [1_{\{\mathbf{s}_2 \in \mathcal{D}\}} - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}_1 \in \mathcal{D}\}}] \\ &\quad + c_F [1_{\{\mathbf{s}_2 \in \mathcal{D}\}} - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}_1 \in \mathcal{D}\}}] \\ &\geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Replacement costs are directly simplified as they do not depend on system states. Given $\mathbf{s}_1 \preceq \mathbf{s}_2$ and Assumption 2, we have $1_{\{\mathbf{s}_2 \in \mathcal{D}\}} - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}_1 \in \mathcal{D}\}} \geq 0$. If $\mathbf{s}_1 \in \mathcal{D}$, then either $\mathbf{s}_2 \in \mathcal{D}$ or $\mathbf{s}_2 \notin \mathcal{D}$. Conversely, if $\mathbf{s}_2 \in \mathcal{D}$, Assumption 2 ensures that $\mathbf{s}_1 \in \mathcal{D}$, implying $1_{\{\mathbf{s}_2 \in \mathcal{D}\}} - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}_1 \in \mathcal{D}\}} \in \{0, 1\}$.

Proof of Lemma 3. Let $\mathbf{s} \preceq \mathbf{s}'$ and $\mathbf{a} \preceq \mathbf{a}'$. For clarity, define $\Delta' = c(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{a}') - c(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{a})$ and $\Delta = c(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}') - c(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a})$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta' &= c(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{a}') - c(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{a}) \\ &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} [c_p^n \cdot 1_{\{a'_n = \text{PM}\}} + c_f^n \cdot 1_{\{a'_n = \text{CM}\}}] \\ &\quad - \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} [c_p^n \cdot 1_{\{a_n = \text{PM}\}} + c_f^n \cdot 1_{\{a_n = \text{CM}\}}] \\ &\quad + c_s \cdot \left[1 - (1 - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}\}}) \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a'_n = \text{DN}\}} \right] \\ &\quad - c_s \cdot \left[1 - (1 - 1_{\{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{D}\}}) \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} \right] \\ &\quad + c_F \cdot 1_{\{\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}\}} - c_F \cdot 1_{\{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{D}\}} \\ &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} c_p^n \cdot [1_{\{a'_n = \text{PM}\}} - 1_{\{a_n = \text{PM}\}}] \\ &\quad + \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} c_f^n \cdot [1_{\{a'_n = \text{CM}\}} - 1_{\{a_n = \text{CM}\}}] \\ &\quad + c_s \cdot (1 - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}\}}) \left[\prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} - \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a'_n = \text{DN}\}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we derive

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta &= c(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}') - c(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}) \\ &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} c_p^n \cdot \left[1_{\{a'_n = \text{PM}\}} - 1_{\{a_n = \text{PM}\}} \right] \\ &\quad + \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} c_f^n \cdot \left[1_{\{a'_n = \text{CM}\}} - 1_{\{a_n = \text{CM}\}} \right] \\ &\quad + c_s \cdot \left(1 - 1_{\{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{D}\}} \right) \left[\prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} - \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a'_n = \text{DN}\}} \right].\end{aligned}$$

Now, computing $\Delta' - \Delta$:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta' - \Delta &= c(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{a}') - c(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{a}) - (c(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}') - c(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a})) \\ &= c_s \cdot \left[\prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} - \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a'_n = \text{DN}\}} \right] \\ &\quad - c_s \cdot 1_{\{\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}\}} \cdot \left[\prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} - \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a'_n = \text{DN}\}} \right] \\ &\quad - c_s \cdot \left[\prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} - \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a'_n = \text{DN}\}} \right] \\ &\quad + c_s \cdot 1_{\{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{D}\}} \cdot \left[\prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} - \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a'_n = \text{DN}\}} \right] \\ &= c_s \cdot \left[\prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} - \prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a'_n = \text{DN}\}} \right] \\ &\quad \times (1_{\{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{D}\}} - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}\}}).\end{aligned}$$

Since $1_{\{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{D}\}} - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}\}}$ takes values in $\{0, -1\}$, we analyze its cases:

- If $\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{D}$, then $\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}$, implying $1_{\{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{D}\}} - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}\}} = 0$.
- If $\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}' \notin \mathcal{D}$, then $1_{\{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{D}\}} - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}\}} = 0$.
- If $\mathbf{s} \notin \mathcal{D}$ and $\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}$, then $1_{\{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{D}\}} - 1_{\{\mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{D}\}} = -1$.

In the latter case, since $\prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a'_n = \text{DN}\}} = 0$ (as the system is down), two scenarios arise:

- If $\prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} = 0$, then $\Delta' - \Delta = 0$.
- If $\prod_{n=1}^N 1_{\{a_n = \text{DN}\}} = 1$, then $\Delta' - \Delta < 0$.

Thus, we conclude that $\Delta' - \Delta \leq 0$, proving the subadditivity of the cost function due to the setup cost.

Proof of Lemma 4. The proof follows directly from the argument provided in Lemma 1. The difference $q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}') - q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a})$ can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}') - q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}) &= \sum_{\mathbf{j} \succeq \mathbf{x}} p_{as(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}'), \mathbf{j}} - \sum_{\mathbf{j} \succeq \mathbf{x}} p_{as(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}), \mathbf{j}} \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{j} \succeq \mathbf{x}} \prod_{n=1}^N \left(q_{as(s_n, a'_n), j_n}^{(n)} - q_{as(s_n, a_n), j_n}^{(n)} \right) \\ &\leq 0.\end{aligned}$$

Since we assume $\mathbf{a} \preceq \mathbf{a}'$, using Assumption 2, which focuses on the wear-out phase, we have $as(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}') \preceq as(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a})$. Thus, $q(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a})$ is element-wise monotonic decreasing with respect to \mathbf{a} .

Proof of Theorem 1. The proof is conducted using induction based on the iterations of the value iteration algorithm, following the approach described in

[1]–[3]. Initially, for all $\bar{\mathbf{s}} \in \mathcal{S}$, it is assumed that $V^0(\bar{\mathbf{s}}) = 0$. Without loss of generality, we have $V^1(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_2) \geq V^1(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_1)$. Now, assume the induction hypothesis $V^\eta(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_2) \geq V^\eta(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_1)$ for $\eta = 1, \dots, \zeta$. Then, for the next iteration $V^{\zeta+1}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_2) = \sum_{\mathbf{z}} p_{\bar{\mathbf{s}}_2, \mathbf{z}} [c(\mathbf{z}, \pi^*(\mathbf{z})) + V^\zeta(as(\mathbf{z}, \pi^*(\mathbf{z})))] \geq \sum_{\mathbf{z}} p_{\bar{\mathbf{s}}_1, \mathbf{z}} \min_{\mathbf{a}} \{c(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{a}) + V^\zeta(as(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{a}))\} = V^{\zeta+1}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_1)$, where the inequality follows from the induction hypothesis, Lemma 1, Lemma 2, and Lemma 4.7.2 in [2]. Therefore, the optimal post-action state bias function is element-wise monotonic increasing with respect to the post-action state.

Proof of Corollary 1. Let $\mathbf{a}^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbf{s}_2)} \{c(\mathbf{s}_2, \mathbf{a}) + V^*(as(\mathbf{s}_2, \mathbf{a}))\}$, then

$$\begin{aligned}J^*(\mathbf{s}_2) &= c(\mathbf{s}_2, \mathbf{a}^*) + V^*(as(\mathbf{s}_2, \mathbf{a}^*)) \\ &\geq c(\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{a}^*) + V^*(as(\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{a}^*)) \\ &\geq \min_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbf{s}_1)} \{c(\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{a}) + V^*(as(\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{a}))\} \\ &= J^*(\mathbf{s}_1).\end{aligned}\tag{7a}$$

The inequality (7a) is valid because the cost function $c(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}^*)$ increases with \mathbf{s} from Lemma 2, and the optimal post-action state bias function $V^*(as(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}^*))$ is shown to be element-wise non-decreasing in \mathbf{s} , as established in Theorem 1.

II. TRANSITION MATRICES

We present the transition matrices for transient states used for the numerical results, which are randomly generated such that they satisfy Assumption 2. We consider two non-decreasing hazard shapes: Weibull shape denoted as h_w and sigmoid shape denoted as h_σ . We first select the shape of the hazard function and its respective parameters. Then, we formulate the following constraint non-linear optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned}\text{minimize} \quad & \sum_{\tau} \left(\frac{(\alpha^{(n)})^T (\mathbf{Q}_S^{(n)})^{\tau-1} \mathbf{q}^{(n)}}{(\alpha^{(n)})^T (\mathbf{Q}_S^{(n)})^{\tau-1} \mathbf{e}} - h_i(\tau) \right)^2 \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \mathbf{q}^{(n)} = 1 - (\alpha^{(n)})^T \mathbf{Q}_S^{(n)} \mathbf{e}, \\ & \mathbf{q}^{(n)} \geq \mathbf{0},\end{aligned}$$

where $i \in \{w, \sigma\}$ and $\mathbf{0}$ is a column vector composed of only 0s. The constrained non-linear optimization problem is addressed using the sequential quadratic programming method

$$\begin{aligned}[4], [5] \cdot \mathbf{Q}_S^{(1)} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.859 & 0.069 & 0.054 & 0.009 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.724 & 0.178 & 0.048 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.588 & 0.280 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.970 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{Q}_S^{(2)} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.007 & 0.468 & 0.257 & 0.053 & 0.136 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.347 & 0.366 & 0.218 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.013 & 0.301 & 0.448 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.006 & 0.396 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{Q}_S^{(3)} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.614 & 0.069 & 0.169 & 0.109 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.602 & 0.257 & 0.118 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.597 & 0.348 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.006 & 0.844 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{Q}_S^{(4)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0007 & 0.486 & 0.302 & 0.054 & 0.109 \\ 0 & 0.0005 & 0.230 & 0.454 & 0.287 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.005 & 0.178 & 0.483 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0004 & 0.404 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0001 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\text{and } \mathbf{Q}_S^{(5)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.105 & 0.634 & 0.133 & 0.125 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.104 & 0 & 0.885 & 0.010 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.106 & 0.300 & 0.295 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.105 & 0.895 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.104 \end{bmatrix}.$$

III. CASE STUDY SETTINGS

We present the transition matrix for transient states used in the case study. As in [6], they use the Weibull distribution to fit the hazard function $h_w(s) = 0.0007s^{0.355}$. Hence, by using the same methodology described in Appendix II, we use the following estimated transition matrix $\mathbf{Q}_S =$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.4190 & 0.2311 & 0.1970 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.5154 & 0.2906 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.7711 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

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